

INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS IN RAW-MATERIAL SECTOR AS AN OVERARCHING SOLUTION IN CIRCULAR ECONOMY

Vessela Petrova

University of Mining and Geology "St. Ivan Rilski", 1700 Sofia; E-mail: vessela.petrova@mgu.bg

ABSTRACT. Circular economy is a key instrument for reducing climate change and transition to green economy. The industrial symbiosis is a circular business model – a concept, discussed as a platform for exchange of materials among business companies in order to achieve sustainability and reduce waste. "Shared use" of wastes as raw-materials results in multiple benefits – economic (reduction of cost to produce raw materials), environmental (reduction of generated waste, reduction of CO₂ emissions, opportunities for applying the green policies), as well as social benefits (creating "green" job positions, support to local communities). A discussion is presented in the paper on industrial symbiosis as an important opportunity for developing a circular economy by the established business model. A survey among thirteen (13) companies from the mineral raw-material sector has been performed and it has proved that companies are aware of the concept, even more – to a certain extent, companies perform the concept in their day-to-day activities. The paper has marked the need of actually mapped networks, which will model a sustainable industrial symbiosis.

Key words: industrial symbiosis, circular economy, mineral raw-material industry

Introduction

Rational use of natural resources is among the most important environment-related considerations, which underlies the bases of the initial European contracts. The roadmap to a resource efficient Europe (COM(2011)0571) is among the key initiatives of the Seventh Environment Action Programme. Deployment of the economic potential of the European Union in order to provide more productive economy concurrently with the use of less resource and converting from linear to circular economy is among the major objectives of the Programme. Adopted in 2018, the Circular Economy Package comprises measures that will assist the stimulation of transition of the European Union to circular economy by increasing the share of recycling and re-use by promoting competitiveness in worldwide plan, enhancing sustainable economic growth and creating new job positions.

Competitive measures for promoting re-use and stimulating the industrial symbiosis – converting the by-product of one sector into a raw material for another are among the elements, comprised by the Circular Economy Package of 2018.

The present report is a discussion on industrial symbiosis as one of the business models in circular economy, a business model that might result in implementation of its principles.

Nature of the concept of industrial symbiosis

Industrial symbiosis has been familiar since the 70-ties of the past century. The concept has been defined as a synergic exchange of refuse flows, by-products, water and energy among individual organisations in a certain area or region.

In its nature, the industrial symbiosis is a sub-sector of industrial ecology, which includes individual industries in a collective approach to competitive advantages, including physical exchange of materials, energy and services (Chertow, 2000). In particular, industrial process wastes may either be used by the processes of the same or another company as a substitute of industrial resources (i.e. water, raw materials, energy) or may be used in the production of

new products to be sold on the market (Albino and Fraccascia, 2015).

The industrial symbiosis is characterised as a systematic approach toward a more sustainable and more integrated industrial system (Chertow and Ehrenfeld, 2012), which identifies business opportunities effecting on the insufficiently used resources (as raw materials, energy, water, opportunities, experience, assets etc.) (Lombardi and Laybourn, 2012). It includes organisations, operating in various sectors, which take part in mutually beneficial exchanges for re-use of wastes and by-products thus inventing innovative approaches for obtaining raw materials and optimising the value of wastes of their specific processes. In addition, the concept is discussed as a practical approach for "improving the resource effectiveness, reducing the generation of waste and green-house gas emissions by exchange of raw materials, energy, by-products among various processes and industries" (Sun et al., 2017). Thus it became included in the background of strategies for promoting transition to circular economy by promoting the transition of flows of resources through multiple cycles in various sectors and supply chains. The success of industrial symbiosis depends on cooperation of the organisations and synergic opportunities, available in the geographical neighbourhood.

Companies that have applied the business model of industrial symbiosis may reduce production costs and thus achieve economic benefits and, in the meantime, create environmental and social benefits for the entire society (Simboli et al., 2015). In this regard, the industrial symbiosis has been recognised as one of the key strategies that support the transition to circular economy (Lopez et al., 2018). Several studies have revealed that industrial symbiosis may be a useful approach of companies to reduce their CO₂ emissions (Sun et al., 2017), which complies with the objectives of the Paris Climate Accords (Nieto et al., 2018).

Conventional methods for assessment of the symbiotic network include assessment of the lifecycle, taking account of the impact on the environment, recycling and re-use of wastes and comparing several referent scenarios. It has always been

focused on reduction of the impact of industrial symbiotic network on the environment in the high-risk business sectors.

Types of industrial symbiosis

The concept of industrial symbiosis finds its expression through "eco-industrial parks". The eco-industrial park is characterised as a community of manufacturing enterprises that cooperate with each other in order to effectively share resources (information, materials, water, energy, infrastructure and natural habitat). The collective benefit is economic

efficiency and benefits in the context of the environment and local communities. The variety of waste flows and industries characterises also the variety of the types of industrial symbiosis. Chertow (2000) is the first one to deliver a systematic description and categorisation of the industrial symbiosis. She detailed study of 18 potential eco-industrial parks models and proposed taxonomy with five defined types of industrial symbiosis based on exchange of resources:

Table 1. Types of industrial symbiosis (Adapted according to Chertow, 2000)

Type of industrial symbiosis	Examples
Exchange of wastes	Collecting and recycling of waste paper, metals etc.
Inner utilisation in the framework of one organisation	Treatment of wastewater from production processes and re-use
External utilisation among organisations – members of a common industrial zone	Waste heat and steam generation
External utilisation among organisations, outside a common industrial zone, however located geographically close to one another	Various materials
External utilisation between organisations – connected by a digital platform	That type of industrial symbiosis provides much more opportunities because of the higher number of potential participants

Analyses of non-hazardous waste - produced and transferred for utilisation in Bulgaria

The major objective of the statistical studies on produced wastes is to provide information about the quantity of produced waste and waste transferred for utilisation. The review of wastes from production processes in Bulgaria

reveals that the mining industry sector occupies the greatest share. The attention has been drawn by the relative dependence between total waste and waste from mining industry (Figure. 1).

Fig. 1. Production waste, total for the country (Bulgaria); Source: Bulgarian National Statistical Institute, www.nsi.bg

Production wastes transferred for utilisation, total for the country (Bulgaria), are presented in Figure 2. The attention has been drawn by the great difference between total

transferred non-hazardous wastes and transferred wastes from the mining industry.

Fig. 2. Transferred for utilisation production waste, total for the country (Bulgaria); Source: Bulgarian National Statistical Institute, www.nsi.bg

Analysis of results from the empirical study and a discussion

The present study has analytical and applied character. Its methodological foundations are based on the development of a survey in an on-line format and carrying out an investigation of intentions and opinions of 13 companies of the mineral raw-material sector. The scope of the survey comprises enterprises of different sizes. The persons who took part in the survey occupy positions in the management and they are responsible for making managerial decisions and actively participate in the development and application of strategies and business models. The survey may not pretend for exhaustiveness, even that leading companies from the mineral resource sector in Bulgaria belong to the scope of the surveyed ones. The summaries of the survey and its results are important and indicative for the formulation of conclusions and recommendations and may also be used as a background for future research.

The answers to the query “Are you aware of the concept for an “industrial symbiosis” – a process, by which waste or by-product of a certain industry or industrial process become raw materials for another industry?” provide convincing results that more than 90% of the management of the surveyed companies is definitely aware of the concept. (Figure 3).

More than 90% of the surveyed persons responded positively to the query “Are you aware of real examples from Bulgaria, concerning the “industrial symbiosis” – instead of being thrown away or destroyed, the excessive resources generated by a certain production may be collected and re-directed to be used as a “new” contribution to another production by one or more companies, thus providing mutual benefit or symbiosis“. The attention is drawn by the fact that

the share of those, who are not aware of real examples from Bulgaria, related to industrial symbiosis is very low – those are at least 8.3 % (Figure 4).

Fig 3. Survey among the raw-material industry companies - question 1

Fig. 4. Survey among the raw-material industry companies - question 2

Examples of a successful process in this regard is the collaboration between the ContourGlobal Maritsa East 3 Thermal Power Plant and Knauf Bulgaria, the companies utilise technical gypsum (produced by the sulphur-treatment installations of the thermal power plant) as a raw material for production of gypsum products. The benefits of that good practice are both economic and environmental.

The cooperation between Aurubis Bulgaria and Haidelberg Devnia Cement, and also Holcim Bulgaria and Titan Zlatna Panega Cement is in the same context. The companies utilise fayalite (the main secondary product of the process of copper recovery from copper concentrates) in the construction process.

The last query in the empirical survey marks the intentions of management concerning the participation of the company into a metabolism as "industrial symbiosis". Seventy five (75) % of the surveyed ones replied positively, 8.3% negatively, and 16.7% consider that industrial symbiosis is not applicable to their business activities. (Figure 5).

Fig. 5. Survey among the raw-material industry companies- question 3

The business benefits resulting due to the application of industrial symbiosis are predominantly economical, related mainly to reduction of the cost for waste management and relevant infrastructure. In the context of "green policies", the environmental benefits are valued more and more – the wastes are utilised as raw materials in other sectors. Care for society and the environment - part of the strategy for corporate social responsibility is another stimulus for companies of the mineral raw material sector (Bakardzhieva, 2010). The major constrains in front the application of industrial symbiosis in Bulgaria are of administrative and economical character. Good communication strategy and coordination among participants is also required. The major emphasis among the barriers is the need of financial instruments, for example for subsidising the treatment of wastes.

Industrial zones and platforms

Industrial zones may be developed as a regional unit, part of a national platform, providing services directly to the participants in the zone.

In Bulgaria, the concept "industrial zone" has not yet obtained a juridical status and zones of that type are formed

completely on a regional basis, i.e. in order to provide communal services and infrastructure.

The platforms for industrial symbiosis are among the main instruments for coordinating the connection between consumers and suppliers of by-products or waste flows as well as sources of innovative technologies and expertise. According to a study of wastes produced in the country (Bulgaria), possible business models for waste treatment and studying the options available in the other countries was carried out within the "Solid Waste Reuse Platform for Balkan" Project. The study revealed that those platforms most substantially contribute to industries with a large number of small and medium-size enterprises that have limited time and human resources to identify the potential opportunities for an industrial symbiosis. The implementation of a successful project of that type requires a strategy for development of a platform, technical expertise, mutual confidence and perfect communication (Denkstatt, 2019).

The industrial symbiosis is characterised with a variety, resulting from the variety of the system elements. The companies affiliated to the industrial symbiotic network, usually come from various industrial sectors. Therefore, they produce various types of wastes and require various types of raw materials. Furthermore, those companies may be affiliated to different supply chains and they would not have cooperated with each other had they not participated in the waste exchange. The principle of variety is a basic one for the industrial symbiotic networks because it allows production of various wastes and requires various raw materials within the same industrial symbiotic network (Fraccascia et al., 2017). In fact, the more various companies are included within an industrial symbiotic network, the higher is the opportunity for establishing industrial-symbiotic interrelations and creating a long lasting sustainable system. In spite of the above, "variety of included participations means variety of interests, preferences and values that might be contradicting" (Chertow, 2004). With regard to the above "organisational cultures" of participating companies are different. The models and management styles vary. The more variety is available in the system, the more complicated and more challenging are the efforts for harmonising and making the strategies of specific companies compliant with the entire network strategy" (Baumgartner et al., 2010).

Conclusions and recommendations

The industrial symbiosis has definitely been characterised as a circular business model, the implementation of an industrial symbiosis results in multiple benefits.

Transparency and active dialogue between different stakeholders, organising of information-exchange events, working groups and meetings for exchange of information among the industries are decisively important for the application of innovative technologies, resulting in understanding the benefits of industrial symbiosis.

In the Bulgarian context, to this date, a strong governmental policy is missing to prepare a Strategy for circular economy and a roadmap that will facilitate the transition from linear to circular economy, which involves the application of industrial symbiosis.

Based on this publication, the following recommendations are proposed:

- An empirical survey proved that the concept is familiar in the mineral raw-material sector; the management bodies are familiar with the good practices in that aspect and recognise the opportunity to enter into a similar symbiotic network. The potential opportunity for applying such a network has practically been defined, even that this happens mainly in large enterprises of the processing industry.
- Elements that will substantially facilitate the establishing of an industrial symbiosis in a national context consist in establishing a national programme or platform for development of industrial symbiosis, mechanisms, supporting the creation of expert groups and scientific projects.
- The platforms for industrial symbiosis, which map the enterprises, are the major instrument for exchange of information, coordinating and planning of practical implementation and in this aspect, the establishing of a working structure of that type is especially important. The platforms are discussed as a channel for establishing an effective connection between potential consumers and suppliers of by-products or waste flows, as well as sources of innovative technologies and expertise.
- The industrial zones are substantially important for planning of future partnerships in order to apply the industrial symbiosis.

- Lopez D., Javier F., Bastein T., Tukker A., 2018. Business model innovation for resource-efficiency, circularity and cleaner production: What 143 cases tell us, *Ecological Economics*, 155, 10.1016/j.ecolecon.2018.03.009.
- Luca F., Giannoccaro I., Vito A., 2017. Rethinking resilience in industrial symbiosis: Conceptualisation and measurements, *Ecological Economics*, 137, 148–162. 10.1016/j.ecolecon.2017.02.026.
- Lombardi D. R., Laybourn P., 2012, Redefining industrial symbiosis, *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 16, 28-37, doi.org/10.1111/j.1530-9290.2011.00444.x
- Roadmap to a Resource Efficient Europe COM(2011) 571, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=ELEX:52011DC0571>
- Simboli A., Raggi A., Pietro R., 2015. Life cycle assessment of process eco-innovations in an SME automotive supply network, *Sustainability*, 7, 13761-13776. 10.3390/su71013761.
- Sun L., Li H., Dong L., Fang K., Ren J., Geng Y., Fujii M., Zhang W., Zhang N., Liu Z., 2017. Eco-benefits assessment on urban industrial symbiosis based on material flows analysis and energy evaluation approach: a case of Liuzhou city, *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 119, 78-88, doi 10.1016/j.resconrec.2016.06.007

References

- Albino V., Luca F., 2015. The industrial symbiosis approach: a classification of business models, *Procedia Environmental Science, Engineering and Management*, 2, 217-223.
- Bakardzhieva R., 2010. Korporativna sotsialna otgovornost – yadro na ustoychivoto razvitiye. Ustoychivo razvitiye i mnogobrazie v Balgariya, Sofiya, IKOPIS.
- Baumgartner R., Jouni K., 2010. Strategic thinking for sustainable development, *Sustainable Development*, 18, 71-75, doi 10.1002/sd.452.
- Chertow M., 2004. Industrial Symbiosis, doi 10.1016/B0-12-176480-X/00557-X.
- Chertow M., 2000. Industrial symbiosis: Literature and taxonomy, *Annual Review of Energy and the Environment*, 25, 313-337, 10.1146/annurev.energy.25.1.313.
- Chertow M., Ehrenfeld J., 2012. Self-organising systems, *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 16, doi 10.1111/j.1530-9290.2011.00450.x.
- Denkstatt, Prouchvane na obrazuvanite otpadatsi v stranata, vazmozhnite biznes modeli za prerabotvaneto im i prouchvane na vazmozhnostite v drugite strani". 2019. https://www.biabg.com/uploads/files/Projects/Combined%20Report_SWAN_denkstatt_190430.pdf
- Fraccascia, L., Il. Giannoccaro, V. Albino, 2017. Rethinking Resilience in Industrial Symbiosis: Conceptualization and Measurements, *Ecological Economics*, 137, 148–162. 10.1016/j.ecolecon.2017.02.026.
- Nieto, J., C. Óscar, M. Luis. 2018. Less than 2 °C? An Economic-Environmental Evaluation of the Paris Agreement, *Ecological Economics*, 146, 69-84. 10.1016/j.ecolecon.2017.10.007.